

Lead-Contaminated Soils and Community Health in Kabwe, Zambia: Evaluating Policy and Remediation Responses

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Abstract

Lead (Pb) contamination remains a persistent public health challenge in Kabwe, Zambia - one of the world's most lead-polluted cities due to historical mining at the former Broken Hill Mine (BHM). This study examines the link between soil contamination, human exposure risks, and the effectiveness of existing policy and remediation interventions. Soil and dust samples were collected from Chowa, Kasanda, Mutwe wa Nsofu, and Makandanyama townships following standard protocols and analysed using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) to determine Pb concentrations. Results revealed Pb levels exceeding international safety thresholds, particularly in residential areas within a 3 km radius of the mine. Despite the implementation of the Zambia Mining and Environmental Remediation and Improvement Project (ZMERIP), remediation outcomes remain uneven due to gaps in regulatory enforcement, limited technical capacity, and inadequate community health monitoring. The study identifies major weaknesses in Zambia's environmental governance - specifically, the absence of clear soil protection standards and enforcement mechanisms - and highlights the need for integrated soil protection and public health strategies. Strengthening legal frameworks, enhancing environmental monitoring, and promoting community-based risk reduction are recommended to safeguard human health and achieve sustainable remediation in mining-affected regions.

Keywords: Lead contamination, Kabwe, Soil pollution, Public health, Remediation, Zambia Mining and Environmental Remediation & Improvement project, Environmental governance.

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Introduction

Soil contamination by heavy metals poses a serious global public health concern, particularly in low and middle-income countries where industrial and mining legacies persist without adequate environmental safeguards (Adnan et

al., 2024; Kapwata et al., 2020). Among heavy metals, lead (Pb) remains one of the most toxic and persistent pollutants, capable of causing irreversible neurological, developmental, and physiological damage even at low exposure levels (Davidovics & DiCicco-Bloom, 2005;

Parithathvi et al., 2024; Shvachiy et al., 2020). The World Health Organization (WHO) identifies Pb exposure as a major contributor to the global burden of disease, accounting for approximately 0.6% of the total global disease burden (Tahir et al., 2024), disproportionately affecting children and pregnant women in developing nations (Torres-Mendoza et al., 2025). In Zambia, the mining sector has historically been the backbone of economic growth (Msoni, 2016); however, it has also generated widespread environmental degradation and left behind significant contamination legacies.

Kabwe, once home to the Broken Hill Mine (BHM), stands as one of the most severely Pb-contaminated cities in the world. Decades of Pb and zinc (Zn) extraction, inadequate waste management, and the absence of systematic rehabilitation have resulted in elevated soil and dust Pb concentrations across residential areas (Bose-O'Reilly et al., 2018). Communities residing near the former mine continue to face heightened risks of Pb exposure through ingestion and inhalation of contaminated soil and dust, consumption of locally grown food, and contact with polluted water sources (Lombe & Katete, 2024; Lombe et al., 2021). Numerous studies have documented elevated blood lead levels (BLLs) among Kabwe's children, with some exceeding internationally accepted safety limits (Bose-O'Reilly et al., 2018; Moonga et al., 2022; Yabe et al., 2020; Yabe et al., 2015), underscoring the intersection of environmental degradation and public health inequity.

In response to these long-standing challenges, the Government of the Republic of Zambia, with support from the World Bank, launched the Zambia Mining and Environmental Remediation and Improvement Project (ZMERIP) to mitigate contamination in Kabwe and other mining-affected areas. The project sought to implement soil remediation, enhance environmental monitoring, and strengthen institutional capacity for environmental governance (MMMD, 2021). Yet, despite these efforts, questions remain regarding the effectiveness and sustainability of remediation outcomes, as well as the adequacy of existing

policy and legislative frameworks in addressing soil contamination and public health protection.

This study examines the persistence of Pb-contaminated soils in Kabwe and evaluates both the technical and policy dimensions of ongoing remediation interventions. It seeks to: (1) assess Pb concentrations in soil and settled dust within affected communities, (2) evaluate the effectiveness of remediation measures implemented under ZMERIP, and (3) identify policy and institutional gaps that hinder effective soil protection and public health responses. By linking environmental science with governance analysis, this paper provides insights into how strengthened policy frameworks and community-centred interventions can reduce exposure risks and promote sustainable public health outcomes in Zambia's mining regions.

Literature Review

Mining, Soil Contamination, and Public Health

Mining activities are among the major anthropogenic sources of soil contamination globally, particularly through the release of heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), arsenic (As), and zinc (Zn). These metals persist in the environment and accumulate in soils, posing long-term ecological and human health risks. Numerous studies have demonstrated that exposure to Pb-contaminated soils is associated with neurodevelopmental disorders in children, renal dysfunction, anaemia, and cardiovascular diseases in adults (Finkelstein et al., 1998; Needleman et al., 1990). The health burden is especially acute in communities adjacent to poorly managed or abandoned mining sites, where Pb-contaminated dust is readily dispersed into living environments (Markus & McBratney, 2001; Zhang et al., 2019).

Zambia's mining legacy, particularly in the Copperbelt and Central provinces, exemplifies the public health consequences of inadequate environmental regulation. Historical mining practices at BHM released substantial quantities of Pb into surrounding soils and sediments. Despite mine closure in 1994, high soil Pb levels remain, exposing generations of residents to chronic contamination (Lombe et al., 2021).

Studies conducted in Kabwe have reported soil lead concentrations exceeding 10,000 mg/kg in some residential zones, far above the U.S. EPA residential safety limit of 1,200 mg/kg (NAKATA et al., 2022; U.S., 2020). This persistent contamination reflects the cumulative effects of poor environmental management, weak enforcement mechanisms, and limited community awareness of exposure pathways.

Policy and Regulatory Frameworks for Soil Protection

Globally, soil protection is increasingly being incorporated into environmental and public health policies. The European Union has taken a leading role through measures such as the European Soil Monitoring Law (Bancheri et al., 2025), while China has implemented a comprehensive regulatory system to address soil pollution, including an administrative liability framework (Lu & Faure, 2020). Additionally, many nations are aligning their efforts with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), recognizing that healthy soils are essential for achieving targets related to food security, clean water, and climate action (Bancheri et al., 2025). However, Zambia's policy landscape remains fragmented. Although the Environmental Management Act (EMA) of 2011 and the Mines and Minerals Development Act (MMDA) of 2015 require Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) and rehabilitation plans, they lack explicit standards for soil quality or contamination thresholds. Furthermore, the absence of continuous monitoring mechanisms and dedicated soil protection legislation constrains effective enforcement (Mulenga, 2022; Wambwa et al., 2023a).

The Zambia Environmental Management Agency (ZEMA) oversees compliance and permitting but is constrained by limited financial and technical capacity (Wambwa et al., 2023b). The ZMERIP, launched in 2017 with World Bank support, represents a significant step toward institutional strengthening and community-level remediation. Nevertheless, its long-term effectiveness depends on policy coherence, sustained funding, and integration with public health surveillance systems.

Comparative analyses from South Africa, Chile, and the European Union illustrate that strong legal instruments, technical guidance documents, and community participation frameworks are critical for successful soil remediation (Bialas & Kozłowski, 2024; Lima et al., 2016). Without these, remediation efforts risk becoming ad hoc and unsustainable. For Zambia, aligning national environmental regulations with international best practices could substantially enhance soil governance and reduce health risks in mining-affected communities.

Lead Exposure Pathways and Health Impacts

Pb exposure occurs primarily through ingestion and inhalation of contaminated soil and dust, with children being particularly vulnerable due to hand-to-mouth behaviours and higher absorption rates. Children may absorb up to 50% of ingested Pb compared to 10 - 15% in adults (Mushak, 1991). Chronic exposure impairs cognitive development, reduces IQ, and can cause behavioural problems (Wilson et al., 2013). In Kabwe, these risks are exacerbated by environmental factors such as poor drainage systems that spread Pb-laden sediments into residential zones and inadequate waste management practices. Despite ongoing health campaigns, medical surveillance and Pb screening coverage remain limited, emphasizing the need for integrated public health and environmental interventions.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The research was conducted in Kabwe District, Central Province, Zambia (Figure 1), once the site of BHM - a major Pb and Zn producer until its closure in 1994. The area remains heavily contaminated with Pb-rich tailings/slag waste. Sampling was carried out in four residential townships, i.e., Chowa, Mutwe wa Nsofu, Kasanda, and Makandanyama, which were identified as contamination hotspots under ZMERIP. A control site located approximately 10 km southwest of the mine served as a baseline reference point, consistent with the ZMERIP (2019) baseline values used for comparison.

Figure 1. GIS Map Showing the Location of the Study Area

Soil Sampling

Soil sampling followed the Chinese National Standard GB/T 17141-1997 for assessing heavy metal contamination in urban soils. Sampling equipment included a stainless-steel auger, trowel, polyethylene bags, and GPS device. In each township, 1 kg soil samples were collected at a depth of 0–20 cm, the zone most affected by atmospheric deposition and human exposure. A total of five soil samples were obtained, two from Zone A (Chowa & Mutwe wa Nsofu), two from Zone B (Kasanda & Makandanyama), and one control sample (Zone C). Each sample was labelled using a three-character identification code (i.e., 1SA, 2SA, 3SB, 4SB, 5SC), where the first number indicated the sample sequence, “S” denoted soil, and “A–C” represented the zone.

Field procedures emphasized contamination control: gloves were changed between samples, tools were rinsed with distilled water, and observations of land use, vegetation, and nearby structures were recorded. All samples were stored in sterile bags within a cooler box and transported to the laboratory within 48 hours for analysis.

Settled Dust Sampling

Settled dust samples were collected following the U.S. EPA (1995) “Residential Sampling for Pb: Protocols for Dust and Soil Sampling”. Three samples were obtained from paved residential yards in Kasanda, Mutwe wa Nsofu, and Makandanyama townships to assess Pb loading

on household surfaces and evaluate the effectiveness of ZMERIP’s soil isolation measure (i.e., paving residential yards with concrete pavers). Dust was collected from 1 m² of paved surface using a clean brush and trowel, following standard wipe-sampling procedures. Each sample’s GPS coordinates, site description, and sampling time were recorded to ensure traceability.

Laboratory Analysis

Sample preparation and analysis were conducted at an accredited commercial laboratory, following established quality control and analytical protocols. Samples were oven-dried, pulverized to a uniform powder, and subjected to aqua regia digestion. The resulting solutions were filtered and diluted to 100 mL with deionised water. Pb concentrations were quantified using Inductively Coupled Plasma–Optical Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). Results were reported on a dry weight basis (mg/kg).

Quality assurance included method blanks, duplicate samples, and in-house reference materials to monitor accuracy and contamination. Calibration checks were conducted to ensure instrument stability. Data were validated following standard laboratory procedures before statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Analysis considered sampling methods, ZMERIP 2019 baseline values, prevailing environmental conditions, and key human activities influencing contamination such as encroachment on the BHM slag dump, increased reclamation and mineral processing, and heavy vehicle movement on unpaved roads and the rail corridor.

Sampling Context and Environmental Setting

Soil and settled dust samples were collected in September 2025 during Kabwe’s warm and dry season (August–November), a period known for elevated dust generation and dispersion. This sampling period closely aligns with that used under ZMERIP (August, 2019), ensuring comparability of environmental conditions. The

sampled townships are predominantly characterised by gravel roads, which serve as major sources of resuspended particulate matter. Kabwe's predominant wind direction (south-east to north-west, with an average wind speed of approximately 52 m/s) (Nakamura, 2022) further influences the movement and distribution of contaminated dust, particularly from historically impacted areas surrounding the former BHM. Settled dust samples were collected exclusively from paved yard surfaces using the standard wipe sampling method to ensure consistency and reliability in assessing dust contamination. Soil samples were taken from land-use areas with varying exposure risks, including a vegetable garden in Chowa, a children's playground in Mukandanyama, and general yard areas in Kasanda and Mutwe wa Nsofu. These land-use differences are significant, as gardens and playgrounds involve frequent soil disturbance and therefore present higher potential for human exposure (Duggan et al., 1985).

Influence of Industrial Activities and Landscape Disturbance

Ongoing industrial activities and landscape disturbances around the closed BHM site continue to shape contamination patterns in nearby communities. Encroachment and

reclamation at the BHM slag dump disturb highly contaminated waste, allowing mine tailings to be redistributed through wind and direct human contact. Additionally, informal re-mining activities, where local youths extract Zn and Pb tailings from the mine canal and dry them along gravel road edges before selling them to processing companies, create new points of exposure and intensify the dispersal of fine contaminated particles. Active mineral processing and smelting operations in and around the former mine area further release airborne particulates and potential Pb emissions, adding to the ambient contaminant load. The network of unpaved access roads and the rail track cutting across the former mine area also contributes to dust mobility; continual vehicular and pedestrian movement generates dust plumes capable of transporting Pb-rich soils into surrounding residential zones. Collectively, these activities destabilize previously remediated areas, amplify dust generation, and significantly heighten the risk of recontamination across the community.

Results and Discussion

Lead concentrations in soil and dust samples

Table 1. Pb Concentrations in Soil and Settled Dust

Township	Soil mg/kg	Dust mg/kg	ZMERIP Baseline*	US-EPA Standard
Chowa	1,560	-	911	1,000
Mutwe wa Nsofu	21,279	17,627	1,571	1,200
Kasanda	4,335	7,080	2,696	1,200
Mukandanyama	5,929	7,347	1,115	400
10km Control	21	-	-	1,200

Note: *Average XRF Pb results

Source: MMMD, (2020)

Laboratory analysis of the five soil and three dust samples revealed markedly elevated concentrations of Pb across residential areas situated near the former BHM (Table 1). Soils collected from Zones A and B contained Pb concentrations ranging between 1,500 and 21,500 mg/kg, significantly exceeding the U.S.

EPA residential soil safety threshold of 400 mg/kg for play areas, 1,000 mg/kg for gardens and 1,200 mg/kg for other yard spaces. The control site (Zone C), located approximately 10 km southwest of the contamination source, recorded Pb levels below 100 mg/kg, confirming the localized nature of

contamination. Pb contamination in Kabwe remains widespread and, in many areas, has worsened compared to the 2019 ZMERIP baseline (Figure 2). Soil Pb concentrations increased by 71% in Chowa, 61% in Kasanda, and 432% in Mukandanyama, indicating significant recontamination despite earlier remediation.

Figure 2. Pb concentrations in Soils - 2025 vs 2019
Source: MMD (2020)

Figure 3. Pb Concentrations in Soil & Dust - 2025

Similarly, settled dust samples from paved residential yards showed elevated Pb concentrations ranging from 1,500 to 17,800 mg/kg, exceeding those measured in soils, demonstrating that airborne and resuspended particulates remain a dominant exposure pathway in Kabwe’s residential areas. Further indicating that even surfaces treated under ZMERIP’s soil isolation measure continue to

accumulate contaminated particulates. These results highlight the limited long-term durability of surface remediation measures, which have been repeatedly undermined by ongoing environmental and industrial disturbances. The persistent high concentrations also confirm that dust deposition continues to drive recontamination of remediated sites, particularly in communities adjacent to the former BHM.

Several factors contribute to this sustained dust-mediated pollution. Gravel road networks generate substantial dust during the warm, dry season, and prevailing southeast-to-northwest winds facilitate long-distance transport and redistribution of Pb-bearing particulates. Ongoing encroachment and informal re-mining of the BHM slag dump disturb large quantities of highly contaminated waste, releasing fresh particulate matter into the surrounding neighbourhoods. In addition, active mineral processing and smelting operations near the closed mine, combined with heavy traffic along unpaved access routes and the rail corridor, intensify dust mobilization and promote the spread of contaminated sediments across residential zones. These environmental and anthropogenic pressures collectively reintroduce Pb into areas previously treated through soil replacement, stabilization, or surface isolation, weakening the long-term effectiveness of ZMERIP interventions.

Effectiveness of Remediation Interventions under ZMERIP

ZMERIP implemented a range of remediation techniques, including phosphate-based soil stabilization, soil replacement, deep tilling, soil dilution, surface isolation, and vegetation cover restoration, which achieved partial success in lowering surface lead contamination, especially in areas where contaminated soil was removed or where concrete pavers were installed. Nonetheless, the effectiveness of these interventions was constrained by several challenges. Remediation methods were applied inconsistently across neighbourhoods, producing uneven outcomes in which some locations showed measurable reductions while others remained highly contaminated. In addition, the lack of maintenance for engineered

barriers such as surface isolation led to recontamination from wind-blown dust originating from nearby tailings. Limited community participation in post-remediation monitoring further contributed to the deterioration of protective measures, including vegetation cover. Compounding these issues, the absence of standardized soil quality benchmarks and weak regulatory enforcement hindered the ability to quantitatively assess progress. Overall, these findings align with earlier evaluations indicating that while ZMERIP made important strides in environmental rehabilitation, it did not establish the long-term sustainability mechanisms needed to maintain reduced exposure levels in affected communities (MMMD, 2021; Mulenga, 2022).

Spatial Trends and Exposure Risk Patterns

Spatial trends in the settled dust data further demonstrate the strong influence of proximity to contamination sources. Households located within 1 km of the mine, particularly in Mutwe wa Nsofu, recorded the highest dust Pb concentrations, consistent with a distance-decay pattern in which exposure declines with increasing distance from the tailings and slag heaps. These findings mirror earlier studies in Kabwe despite surface remediation interventions (NAKATA et al., 2022; Wekumbura et al., 2025), which similarly documented residual contamination despite surface remediation. This trend reflects the influence of prevailing wind direction and surface runoff, which transport Pb-laden particles into residential areas. Children in these neighbourhoods face the greatest exposure risk due to frequent outdoor play, hand-to-mouth behaviours, and limited awareness of soil contamination hazards. Given that Pb does not degrade over time, the persistence of high soil Pb levels implies a continuous cycle of exposure through resuspended dust, contaminated produce, and direct soil contact. These patterns underline the urgency for integrated environmental health monitoring, including periodic soil testing, biomonitoring of BLLs, and sustained community education.

Public Health Implications

The high concentrations of Pb found in residential soils and dust in Kabwe have significant implications for community health, particularly among children under five years and pregnant women, who are most vulnerable to the toxic effects of Pb exposure. Chronic exposure can cause neurological impairment, behavioural disorders, reduced IQ, and growth retardation in children (Finkelstein et al., 1998; Needleman et al., 1990). In adults, prolonged Pb exposure contributes to hypertension, renal dysfunction, and anaemia.

Despite sporadic health screening campaigns, routine BLL testing remains limited, and health surveillance systems lack integration with environmental monitoring programs. Public health efforts have been further constrained by inadequate risk communication and minimal collaboration between health and environmental agencies. The absence of a national soil contamination registry or Pb exposure surveillance framework hinders the identification of high-risk populations and the design of targeted interventions.

These gaps underscore the need to mainstream soil protection into Zambia's public health policy framework, ensuring that environmental contamination is recognized as a determinant of health. Cross-sectoral collaboration between the Ministry of Health, Zambia Environmental Management Agency (ZEMA), and local authorities is essential for effective surveillance, early detection, and prevention of Pb-related illnesses.

Policy and Institutional Gaps

The persistence of contamination in Kabwe reflects broader structural weaknesses in Zambia's environmental governance system. The current legal framework, anchored in the Environmental Management Act (EMA) of 2011 and the Mines and Minerals Development Act (MMDA) of 2015, focuses primarily on environmental impact assessments and mine closure procedures, but lacks specific soil protection standards, remediation guidelines, and post-closure liability mechanisms. Moreover, overlapping institutional mandates

between the Ministry of Mines and Minerals Development (MMMD) and ZEMA often result in regulatory ambiguity, while limited technical and financial resources reduce enforcement capacity. The lack of a dedicated fund for long-term remediation and monitoring exacerbates the problem, leaving contaminated communities reliant on short-term, donor-driven projects.

Internationally, countries such as Spain, China, and Germany have demonstrated that binding soil quality standards, liability frameworks for polluters, and national remediation strategies are key to achieving sustainable outcomes (Ramon & Lull, 2019; Sun et al., 2019). Zambia can draw lessons from these models to design a national soil protection policy that integrates health, environment, and development priorities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study demonstrates that soil and dust contamination by Pb remains a major environmental and public health concern in Kabwe, Zambia, despite decades of mine closure and recent remediation interventions under ZMERIP. Laboratory analyses revealed that Pb concentrations in residential soils within a 3 km radius of the former Broken Hill Mine (BHM) significantly exceed international safety thresholds, underscoring persistent exposure risks to local populations. Children, due to their physiological susceptibility and behavioural patterns, are the most vulnerable group, facing lifelong cognitive and developmental consequences from chronic Pb exposure.

The findings highlight both technical and institutional deficiencies in Zambia's approach to soil protection and environmental health management. Although ZMERIP has achieved localized improvements through soil replacement, stabilization, and surface isolation, the overall remediation outcomes remain inconsistent. This inconsistency reflects deeper systemic challenges, including fragmented environmental governance, inadequate enforcement of environmental regulations, absence of soil contamination standards, and limited integration of public health surveillance into environmental management systems.

Addressing the Pb contamination crisis in Kabwe requires a paradigm shift from short-term, project-based interventions toward a sustainable, policy-driven framework that unites environmental rehabilitation with public health protection. Strengthening soil protection governance and establishing clear accountability mechanisms for pollution prevention and remediation will be essential to prevent future contamination and to protect vulnerable populations from exposure-related health impacts.

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance soil protection and safeguard public health in Zambia's mining-affected regions:

Establish National Soil Protection Standards and Guidelines

To strengthen soil management in mining-affected regions, Zambia should develop and implement national soil quality standards that define permissible heavy metal concentrations in line with WHO and UNEP benchmarks. These standards should be supported by clear soil contamination assessment and remediation protocols, with provisions for regular review and updating to reflect evolving scientific and environmental conditions.

Integrate Environmental and Public Health Surveillance

A coordinated monitoring framework between the Ministry of Health and ZEMA is needed to jointly track soil contamination patterns and population blood lead levels. Institutionalized data sharing will improve early detection of exposure risks and facilitate timely, targeted public health interventions within affected communities.

Strengthen Institutional Capacity and Coordination

Improving soil protection requires clearer role delineation among regulatory bodies, particularly MMMD, ZEMA, and local authorities, to ensure consistent enforcement of environmental regulations. Sustained financial support should be allocated to routine inspections, laboratory

testing, and community awareness activities aimed at reducing lead exposure risks.

Promote Sustainable and Community-Based Remediation

Long-term remediation success depends on active community involvement in maintaining treated sites, restoring vegetation cover, and participating in environmental education initiatives. Adoption of low-cost and locally appropriate technologies, such as phytoremediation, soil capping, and improved drainage systems, can further help minimize recontamination and reduce lead exposure in vulnerable neighbourhoods.

Strengthen EPF Financing and Scope for Soil Protection and Public Health

The Environmental Protection Fund (EPF) should be strengthened to explicitly support long-term soil protection and remediation of contamination hotspots in mining-affected regions, including Kabwe. This requires expanding the Fund's mandate to cover legacy pollution, abandoned mine sites, and areas where contaminated soils pose direct public health risks, especially to children. To ensure sustainable financing, the EPF should be supplemented by a dedicated share of mining royalties, environmental levies, and penalties for environmental non-compliance. This broader financing base would enable systematic remediation of contaminated soils, rehabilitation of degraded land, and reduction of human exposure to hazardous metals across affected communities.

Mainstream Soil Protection into Health and Development Policy

Soil contamination management should be integrated into Zambia's National Health Policy and National Development Plans, recognizing environmental degradation as a critical determinant of public health. Strengthening this policy alignment will ensure that soil protection is treated as both an environmental and health priority. Additionally, these national strategies should be harmonized with the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly SDG 3 on Good Health and Well-being and SDG 15 on Life on Land, to support a coherent,

internationally aligned framework for reducing contamination and protecting vulnerable communities

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no financial or personal conflicts of interest that could have influenced the conduct or outcomes of this study. However, the research was carried out in a context where certain institutional and stakeholder sensitivities posed operational limitations. Access to community blood lead level (BLL) data at the government health facility was not granted, and permission to collect samples directly from the tailings dam was denied due to mine operator restrictions and ongoing informal re-mining activities. While these constraints restricted the scope of data collection, they did not introduce any conflicts of interest and were managed in accordance with ethical research practices and the study's approved methodology.

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